

Prototype Anchoring for Image Classification Tasks

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Abstract—In this paper, we aim at improving the performance of a deep learning model towards image classification tasks, proposing a novel anchor-based training methodology, named *Prototype Anchoring for Image Classification* (PAIC). The PAIC method, guided by the insights provided in the anchor-based object detection methodologies, proposes to train a model to learn percentage changes of the class labels with respect to defined anchors, rather than learning directly the class labels. The anchors are defined as the class centers at the output of the model conventionally trained with the class labels (i.e., prototypes) for only a few epochs. Then, during the test phase, the predictions are converted back to the original class label space, and the performance is evaluated. The effectiveness of the PAIC method is validated on four datasets.

Index Terms—anchoring, prototype, image classification

I. INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we deal with image classification tasks, i.e., tasks of assigning class labels to images based on their visual content [1]. In the related literature, several training methodologies are employed for addressing image classification tasks. For example, in the conventional supervised approach of the deep learning era [2], images are introduced to a deep neural network, and through multiple levels of transformation, an output is produced which followed by the softmax operation, indicates the probability of each image to belong to each of the classes of the task. The output of the network also reveals the similarities of the samples with the classes. The network is trained with the class labels using commonly the cross entropy loss, suppressing the aforementioned similarities with the class labels, except for the correct label.

However, the aforementioned similarities usually convey useful information, while also training with one-hot class labels can lead to over-fitting. Hence, another approach for training a deep neural model, closely associated with knowledge distillation methods [3]–[5], uses the so-called soft labels which reveal these similarities. In this training approach, the models are trained both with original class labels and the soft labels, providing improved performance, compared to the conventional supervised training.

Another approach for improving the training process and achieving in turn better performance in terms of accuracy, consists in label smoothing [6], [7], where the labels are computed as a weighted average of the ground truth labels and the uniform distribution over labels. Finally, another established training approach for improving the performance

of a deep learning model towards a vision recognition task is to introduce additional regularization objectives, including a plethora of methods [8], [9].

In this paper, we aim to improve the baseline performance of a deep learning model, considering image classification tasks. To accomplish this goal, we propose a training methodology with inspiration drawn from the anchored-based object detection methodologies [10]–[13]. The main idea behind the aforementioned methodologies, where the goal is to predict the bounding boxes of objects of interest, is that it is easier for the network to learn offsets instead of learning absolute coordinates. That is, the network is provided with predefined boxes, also known as anchors, and the objective is re-formulated as prediction of offsets, instead of predicting the coordinates. For example, the SSD detector learns the logarithm of the ratio between the ground truth coordinates (center, and width and height) and the anchor’s coordinates.

The anchor-based training idea has also been utilized for addressing other tasks except for object detection. For example, it has also been applied considering time-series forecasting tasks in a recent work [14]. In this paper, where the task is formulated as the prediction of electric load demand of the 24 hours of the next day (i.e., the target day), the authors instead of learning directly the load demand of the target day, propose to learn a percentage change of the electric load of the target day with respect to an anchor. As anchor, they propose to use the electric load of the day one week prior the target day. Another example is an anchor-based approach for facial landmark localization which proposes to regress the offsets against each of the predefined anchors [15].

In this paper, we introduce this idea to more challenging image classification tasks, compared to the regression tasks that have previously been successfully addressed. That is, we propose a novel anchor-based training approach, named *Prototype Anchoring for Image Classification* (PAIC). More specifically, considering an image classification task, we correspondingly propose to define an anchor, and instead of learning the class label, to learn a percentage change of the one-hot class label with respect to the defined anchor. As it will be explained in the subsequent sections, we propose to compute the anchors as the class centers (i.e., prototypes) at the output layer of a model conventionally trained for a few epochs.

The proposed anchor-based training methodology is model-agnostic, i.e., it can be applied to any deep learning model

regardless of their complexity, significantly improving their performance, as it experimentally validated on four image classification datasets. Finally, it should be emphasized that our goal is to improve the classification performance of deep learning models towards a classification task proposing a novel training methodology rather than a specified model architecture. That is, PAIC is orthogonal to existing models and it could be readily combined with most existing ones for further improving their classification performance.

The remainder of the manuscript is structured as follows. Section II presents in detail the proposed prototype anchoring methodology for image classification tasks. Subsequently, in Section III the experimental evaluation of the proposed method is provided. Finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section IV.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

In this paper we propose a training methodology for image classification tasks, aiming to improve the classification performance in terms of accuracy. The proposed method, named *Prototype Anchoring for Image Classification* (PAIC), is inspired by insights of anchored-based object detection literature [10]–[13]. This line of research proposes to learn an offset of the actual coordinates of the object bounding box with respect to a predefined anchor, instead of learning to predict them directly.

In this work, instead of training a network with the original class labels of the image classification task at hand in order to directly learn the desired classes (typically using the cross entropy loss), we propose to train a network to learn percentage changes of the one-hot class labels with respect to the defined anchors. For doing so, we calculate the anchors as follows. We first train the network for only a few epochs using the class labels and the cross entropy loss. This way, we acquire the representations of the training samples at the output of the network and we use them in order to calculate the class prototypes, i.e., the mean vectors of each class (class centers), followed by the softmax operation, in order to transform them into values between 0 and 1, summing to 1, and use them as anchors. An overview of the proposed framework is given in Fig. 1.

More specifically, we consider a C -class classification task, and the labeled data $\{\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{c}_i\}_{i=1}^N$, where $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^D$ is an input vector and D its dimensionality, and $\mathbf{c}_i \in \mathbb{Z}^C$ corresponds to its C -dimensional one-hot class label. For an input space $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^D$ and an output space $\mathcal{F} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^C$, we also consider a deep neural network $f(\cdot; \mathcal{W}) : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{F}$ with set of parameters \mathcal{W} , which transforms its input vector to a C -dimensional vector. That is, $f(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathcal{W}) \in \mathcal{F}$ corresponds to the output vector of $\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathcal{X}$ given by the network f with parameters \mathcal{W} .

Considering the anchor computation, we first train the network for only a few epochs with the class labels using cross entropy loss, and we extract the output representations, $f(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathcal{W}_e^*)$, $i = 1, \dots, N$ (as \mathcal{W}_e^* are denoted the parameters conventionally trained for e epochs). The anchors for each class are then computed as the class centers (i.e., mean vectors)

of the extracted representations. That is, the anchor for the l -th class $\mathbf{a}^l \in \mathbb{R}^C$, $l \in \{1, \dots, C\}$ (where $l = \arg \max \mathbf{c}$) is calculated as:

$$\mathbf{a}^l = \sigma \left(\frac{1}{|\mathcal{K}^l|} \sum_{f(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathcal{W}_e^*) \in \mathcal{K}^l} f(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathcal{W}_e^*) \right), \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ denotes the softmax operation and \mathcal{K}^l denotes the set of samples belonging to the class l .

Then, instead of training the model $f(\cdot; \mathcal{W})$ to predict the class label \mathbf{c}_i for a sample i , we propose to define the anchor \mathbf{a}^l , such that $l = \arg \max \mathbf{c}_i$, and train the model to predict the percentage change of the class label with respect to the corresponding anchor. That is, each sample is associated with a specific anchor, based on its class label. Thus, the target for training the model for a sample i is formulated as follows:

$$\mathbf{t}_{PAIC}^i = \frac{\mathbf{c}_i}{\mathbf{a}_{l=\arg \max \mathbf{c}_i}^l} - 1. \quad (2)$$

We use the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss to train the network with the new targets \mathbf{t}_{PAIC} :

$$\mathcal{J} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_1^N (\mathbf{t}_{PAIC}^i - \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{PAIC}^i)^2. \quad (3)$$

After training, i.e., after minimizing (3), the network $f(\cdot; \mathcal{W}^*)$ is trained to predict a percentage change according to (2). Then, during the test phase, considering the corresponding set of test samples, $\{\mathbf{y}_k, \mathbf{r}_k\}_{k=1}^K$, where $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^D$, and $\mathbf{r}_k \in \mathbb{Z}^C$, the inverse transformation is performed, so that the predictions for the test samples are converted back to the original space of the class labels, in order to evaluate the accuracy of the method in predicting the correct class labels. Since each anchor is associated with the class of each sample, in order to avoid employing such information in the test phase, we do not use the anchor \mathbf{a}^l belonging to same class as the test sample, i.e., $l = \arg \max \mathbf{r}_k$, but instead the nearest (in terms of the Euclidean distance) anchor in the output space, denoted as \mathbf{a}_{test}^k . That is, for the set \mathcal{A} of the anchors, $\mathbf{a}_{test}^k = \arg \min_{\mathbf{a}^m \in \mathcal{A}} \|f(\mathbf{y}_k; \mathcal{W}^*) - \mathbf{a}^m\|$.

The aforementioned transformation back to the class label space is formulated as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{r}}_k = \mathbf{a}_{test}^k \cdot (f(\mathbf{y}_k; \mathcal{W}^*) + 1), \quad (4)$$

where $f(\mathbf{y}_k; \mathcal{W}^*) = \hat{\mathbf{t}}_{PAIC}^k$. In this way, the class label predictions of the proposed PAIC method are obtained, and the performance of method can be evaluated and be compared with the conventional approaches.

It should be also emphasized, that in this paper, we propose a training pipeline for classification tasks, drawing inspiration from the anchor-based object detection methods. To accomplish this goal, as discussed above, we propose to use as anchors the class centers at the output space of a conventionally trained model. We note that this is crucially different than a soft-labeling approach, which could use these anchors as soft labels for training the network. We also

Fig. 1. Training and test phases of the proposed PAIC methodology: In the training phase, first a model is conventionally trained so as to extract the output representations and compute the anchors. Then, PAIC proposes to train a model in order to predict percentage changes of the class labels w.r.t to the anchors. Finally, during the test phase the predictions are converted back to the original class label space, so that the accuracy of the model in predicting the correct class labels can be evaluated.

experimentally validate the difference and the superiority over such an approach. Finally, it should be noted that different approaches for defining the anchors in an online manner could be investigated [16], [17].

III. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

In this paper, we have conducted experiments on four datasets for evaluating the performance of the proposed anchor-based training method. The datasets' and the networks' descriptions, along with the evaluation metrics and implementation details, and finally the experimental results are provided in the subsequent subsections.

A. Datasets

Four datasets are used for evaluating the effectiveness of the proposed PAIC method, i.e., UCF-101 [18], Cifar-10 [19], Event Recognition in Aerial videos (ERA) [20], and Biased Action Recognition (BAR) [21]. The utilized datasets vary in terms of size, ranging from 1,473 to 50,000 training images, in terms of image resolution, including images of size 32×32 and 640×640 , and also in terms of number of classes, ranging from 6 to 101 classes.

More specifically, UCF-101 is an action recognition data set of 13,320 YouTube action videos, consisting of 101 action categories. The middle frame is derived from each video, and the train and test sets are formed according to the original splits [18]. Thus, the train set contains 9,537 images, while the test set contains 3,783 images. Images are of size 320×240 . Cifar-10 consists of 50,000 train images and 10,000 test images divided into 10 classes. Images are of size 32×32 . ERA dataset is an event recognition in unconstrained aerial videos.

It consists of 1,473 train images and 1,391 test images, divided into 25 event classes. Images are of size 640×640 . BAR is a real-world image dataset with six action classes which are biased to distinct places. The dataset consists of 1,941 train images and 654 test images. All images of the BAR dataset are over 400×300 . Images in all the the datasets, apart from Cifar-10, are resized to 224×224 .

B. Network Architectures

Network architectures of varying complexity are used in all the datasets. More specifically, in the UCF-101, ERA, and BAR datasets, ResNet-18 [22] and Wide-ResNet-50-2 [23] (abbreviated as WRN-50-2), pretrained on ImageNet weights, are used. A linear layer is added to the output of the networks, with neurons equivalent to the number of the classes of each dataset. In the Cifar-10 dataset, two networks for accepting input images of size 32×32 are utilized, in order to avoid image resizing and interpolation by $\times 7$. That is, a simple lightweight model, consisting of two convolutional layers with six and sixteen kernels of size 5×5 respectively and three fully connected layers ($128 \times 64 \times 10$), and a heavyweight modified Wide-ResNet-28-10 model (abbreviated as WRN-28-10).

C. Evaluation Metrics

Test accuracy is used to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed training methodology. Training and test time in terms of seconds are also reported.

D. Implementation Details

The proposed PAIC method was implemented using the PyTorch framework. The networks are trained using the mini-

batch gradient descent, with a mini-batch of 32 samples. The learning rate (lr) is set to 0.001, and the momentum is 0.9. The networks are trained for 100 epochs in total on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 with 24 GB of GPU memory. That is, the baseline models are trained for 100 epochs, while for the PAIC method, the models are trained with the original class labels for 10 epochs (denoted as epoch of anchoring), in order to compute the anchors, and then the rest 90 epochs are trained with the proposed methodology.

It should be noted that the above lr is optimal for both the compared approaches, i.e., baseline and PAIC. To this aim, we also provide indicative evaluation results on the UCF-101 dataset, using the ResNet-18 model for different values of lr. The results are presented in Table I. As baseline it is denoted a model of identical architecture, trained with the original class labels. Best performance is printed in bold considering the two compared methods, while best performance of each method is underlined. As it is shown, the used lr is the optimal for both the methods, while it is also demonstrated that the PAIC method improves the baseline accuracy for all the considered values of lr.

Finally, considering the epoch of anchoring, it should be mentioned that the PAIC method can improve the baseline performance for different epochs of anchoring. Representative experimental results are provided in Table II, validating the aforementioned claim.

TABLE I
UCF-101: TEST ACCURACY FOR VARIOUS LRS USING THE RESNET-18 MODEL [22].

Method	Learning Rate		
	0.01	0.001	0.0001
Baseline	70.288	<u>72.403</u>	70.579
PAIC	71.028	74.174	72.218

TABLE II
UCF-101: TEST ACCURACY FOR DIFFERENT EPOCHS OF ANCHORING USING THE RESNET-18 MODEL [22] (BASELINE: 72.403).

Epoch	Test Accuracy
5	73.222
10	74.174
20	72.746

E. Experimental Results

In this section, we provide the experimental results of the conducted experiments on the four utilized datasets. We compare the performance of the proposed PAIC method in terms of test accuracy against the baseline. As mentioned, as baseline we denote a model of identical architecture, trained with the original class labels using the conventional supervised loss. Best performance is printed in bold.

First, in Table III, the experimental results on Cifar-10 dataset are provided, for both the lightweight and the relatively heavyweights models. As it is demonstrated, the proposed

anchor-based methodology achieves considerably improved classification performance against the baseline in both the considered cases, validating the effectiveness of the methodology for models of different complexity.

Subsequently, in Table IV the evaluation results on the rest three datasets are provided, using the ResNet-18 model. As it can be observed, the PAIC method accomplishes superior performance over the baseline approach in all the considered datasets. The corresponding results using the heaviest WRN-50-2 model, are provided in Table V, validating the aforementioned remarks. For example, as it is demonstrated, the PAIC training method achieves improvements of up to 3 units in terms of accuracy on the BAR dataset.

TABLE III
CIFAR-10: TEST ACCURACY FOR THE PROPOSED METHOD AGAINST THE BASELINE USING BOTH THE UTILIZED MODELS.

Method	Lightweight	WRN-28-10 [23]
Baseline	65.660	89.130
PAIC	67.130	91.440

TABLE IV
TEST ACCURACY FOR THE PROPOSED METHOD AGAINST THE BASELINE USING THE RESNET-18 MODEL [22].

Dataset	Baseline	PAIC
UCF-101	72.403	74.174
BAR	61.621	63.150
ERA	54.565	55.356

TABLE V
TEST ACCURACY FOR THE PROPOSED METHOD AGAINST THE BASELINE USING THE WRN-50-2 MODEL [23].

Dataset	Baseline	PAIC
UCF-101	78.853	79.170
BAR	70.183	73.547
ERA	56.506	59.310

Regarding the computational complexity of the proposed anchor-based training methodology, the PAIC method negligibly affects the training time, since the anchors are computed once. For example, considering the UCF-101 dataset, which is the more computationally demanding out of the utilized datasets, with regard to the number of classes (and in turn the dimension of the output representations), the whole process of anchor computation takes 10.279 secs. The training time per epoch is similar for the proposed and the baseline approaches (1 epoch of the PAIC training takes 13.370 secs, while 1 epoch of conventional training takes 14.943 secs). Considering the test (inference) time, the proposed method is slower than the baseline evaluation, since it includes the search in the output space for finding the nearest anchor. Again, in the UCF-101 dataset, the whole evaluation takes 9.116 secs considering the PAIC methodology, while it takes 4.219 secs, remaining however a fast process.

Finally, as it was previously noted, the proposed anchor-based training methodology, which uses as anchors the class centers at the output space of the network, is different from a soft-label process, which could use as soft-labels the aforementioned anchors to directly train the model. That is, the PAIC method proposes to learn percentage changes with respect to the anchors. In order to experimentally highlight this difference, we also perform experiments using the computed anchors as soft labels for training a model. That is, the class centers at the output of a model trained with the class labels, followed by the softmax operation to transform them into values between 0 and 1, are used as the soft labels. Thus, instead of using the class label of each sample to train the model, we use its corresponding soft label, based on the class that sample belongs. This soft label reveals the similarities of all the samples of this certain class with all the classes of the task. We train the model using the MSE loss, with the same experimental setup, and we provide indicative experiments on the UCF-101 dataset, using the ResNet-18 model. The experimental results are provided in Table VI. As it can be observed the soft-labeling approach achieves improved performance as compared to the baseline, however is notably worse as compared to the proposed approach.

TABLE VI
TEST ACCURACY FOR THE PROPOSED METHOD AGAINST THE
SOFT-LABELING METHOD USING THE PROPOSED ANCHORS, ON THE
UCF-101 DATASET USING THE RESNET-18 MODEL [22].

Method	Test Accuracy
Baseline	72.403
Soft-labeling	73.090
PAIC	74.174

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we deal with image classification tasks. We aim at improving the performance of a model, proposing a novel anchor-based training pipeline. The PAIC methodology proposes to train a model to learn percentage changes of the class labels with respect to defined anchors, rather than learning directly the class labels. We define as anchors, the class centers at the output of the model trained with the original class labels for only a few epochs. Then during the test phase, the predictions are converted back to the original class label space, and the performance is evaluated. The effectiveness of PAIC is validated on four datasets, using model architectures of varying complexity.

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REFERENCES

[1] Dengsheng Lu and Qihao Weng, "A survey of image classification methods and techniques for improving classification performance," *International journal of Remote sensing*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 823–870, 2007.

[2] Waseem Rawat and Zenghui Wang, "Deep convolutional neural networks for image classification: A comprehensive review," *Neural computation*, vol. 29, no. 9, pp. 2352–2449, 2017.

[3] Zhenyu Zhang, Xiaobo Shu, Bowen Yu, Tingwen Liu, Jiapeng Zhao, Quangan Li, and Li Guo, "Distilling knowledge from well-informed soft labels for neural relation extraction," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2020, vol. 34, pp. 9620–9627.

[4] Maria Tzelepi and Anastasios Tefas, "Efficient training of lightweight neural networks using online self-acquired knowledge distillation," in *2021 IEEE International Conference on Multimedia and Expo (ICME)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1–6.

[5] Maria Tzelepi, Charalampos Symeonidis, Nikos Nikolaidis, and Anastasios Tefas, "Multilayer online self-acquired knowledge distillation," in *2022 26th International Conference on Pattern Recognition (ICPR)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 4822–4828.

[6] Rafael Müller, Simon Kornblith, and Geoffrey E Hinton, "When does label smoothing help?," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 32, 2019.

[7] Chang-Bin Zhang, Peng-Tao Jiang, Qibin Hou, Yunchao Wei, Qi Han, Zhen Li, and Ming-Ming Cheng, "Delving deep into label smoothing," *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, vol. 30, pp. 5984–5996, 2021.

[8] Jan Kukačka, Vladimir Golkov, and Daniel Cremers, "Regularization for deep learning: A taxonomy," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1710.10686*, 2017.

[9] Maria Tzelepi and Anastasios Tefas, "Improving the performance of lightweight cnns for binary classification using quadratic mutual information regularization," *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 106, pp. 107407, 2020.

[10] Shaoqing Ren, Kaiming He, Ross Girshick, and Jian Sun, "Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 28, 2015.

[11] Wei Liu, Dragomir Anguelov, Dumitru Erhan, Christian Szegedy, Scott Reed, Cheng-Yang Fu, and Alexander C Berg, "Ssd: Single shot multi-box detector," in *European conference on computer vision*. Springer, 2016, pp. 21–37.

[12] Kaiming He, Georgia Gkioxari, Piotr Dollár, and Ross Girshick, "Mask r-cnn," in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, 2017, pp. 2961–2969.

[13] Tsung-Yi Lin, Priya Goyal, Ross Girshick, Kaiming He, and Piotr Dollár, "Focal loss for dense object detection," in *Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision*, 2017, pp. 2980–2988.

[14] Maria Tzelepi, Paraskevi Nousi, and Anastasios Tefas, "Improving electric load demand forecasting with anchor-based forecasting method," in *ICASSP 2023-2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–5.

[15] Zixuan Xu, Banghui Li, Ye Yuan, and Miao Geng, "Anchorface: An anchor-based facial landmark detector across large poses," in *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 2021, vol. 35, pp. 3092–3100.

[16] Lukas Ruff, Robert Vandermeulen, Nico Goernitz, Lucas Deecke, Shoaib Ahmed Siddiqui, Alexander Binder, Emmanuel Müller, and Marius Kloft, "Deep one-class classification," in *International conference on machine learning*. PMLR, 2018, pp. 4393–4402.

[17] Vasileios Mygdalis and Ioannis Pitas, "Hyperspherical class prototypes for adversarial robustness," *Pattern Recognition*, vol. 125, pp. 108527, 2022.

[18] Khurram Soomro, Amir Roshan Zamir, and Mubarak Shah, "Ucf101: A dataset of 101 human actions classes from videos in the wild," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1212.0402*, 2012.

[19] Alex Krizhevsky, Geoffrey Hinton, et al., "Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images," 2009.

[20] L. Mou, Y. Hua, P. Jin, and X. X. Zhu, "ERA: A dataset and deep learning benchmark for event recognition in aerial videos," *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Magazine*, in press.

[21] Junhyun Nam, Hyuntak Cha, Sungsoo Ahn, Jaeho Lee, and Jinwoo Shin, "Learning from failure: De-biasing classifier from biased classifier," *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, vol. 33, pp. 20673–20684, 2020.

[22] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2016, pp. 770–778.

[23] Sergey Zagoruyko and Nikos Komodakis, "Wide residual networks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1605.07146*, 2016.